

ARTS

HISTORICAL MONUMENTS AND TOURISM IN NAKHCHIVAN

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Abstract

Historical and cultural monuments are significant factors influencing the development of tourism and enhancing a country's appeal to tourists. Visitors to any country are often interested in its history and material cultural artifacts that reflect its way of life. This article discusses the promotion of cultural heritage in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic through tourism on a global scale.

Keywords: monument, architecture, tourism, promotion, travel, tourist.

Azerbaijan, being one of the earliest cradles of human civilization, is rich in historical-architectural and cultural monuments. From ancient human settlements to over six thousand historical-architectural monuments from the Middle Ages, the country boasts a vast heritage.

It should be noted that historical and cultural monuments are crucial factors that influence the development of tourism and enhance a country's attractiveness to tourists. Visitors to any country are often drawn to its history and material culture, which reflects the way of life. In turn, every country uses its cultural heritage to prove its ancient roots and its role in the formation of human civilization, presenting it to the world. Thus, tourism plays a significant role in promoting a country's cultural heritage globally.

Historical-cultural tourism is an activity aimed at studying the historical and cultural monuments, museums, traditions, and lifestyle of a particular place. (1, page-18)

Architectural monuments, regardless of the period in which they were built, are unique for their architectural style, beauty, and distinctiveness of both their time and the present. Historical monuments, on the other hand, may not hold as much significance from an architectural standpoint but are renowned for their association with significant battles or events, or for having hosted prominent figures. It is these types of monuments that are predominantly utilized in tourism.

According to tourism experts, countries that aim to attract tourists year-round place special emphasis on the development of historical and cultural tourism (4, p.183). This is because historical-cultural tourism operates independently of seasonal relevance. Excursions are undertaken with the purpose of gaining knowledge. In addition to being one of the most widespread forms of tourism managed by travel agencies, it reflects people's desire to familiarize themselves with the historical, cultural, and natural attractions of various regions and countries.

Tourism cannot be imagined without cultural-historical tourism. Any tourist traveling to a country seeks to learn about its culture and history. By participating in educational excursions, they become acquainted with the country's cultural and historical heritage.

In the ancient land of Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan, there are numerous monuments adorned with high artistic ornamentation. Among these are the world-renowned Momine Khatun Mausoleum, built by the famous Azerbaijani architect Ajami Abubakr oglu, and the Yusif Kuseyir oglu memorial complex, also constructed by Ajami in 1162. Other notable monuments include the Garabaghlar Historical-Architectural Complex in the village of Garabaghlar in Sharur District, the Gulustan Mausoleum in Julfa District, the 15th-19th century Ordubad Cultural Reserve in the city of Ordubad, and ancient archaeological sites such as the ruins of the ancient city of Nakhchivan from the 2nd millennium BC to the Middle Ages. Additionally, the Bronze Age sites such as the Gizilburun settlement and the I-II Gizilbulag temples in Babek District, the Bronze Age Chalxanqala Fortress and kurgans in Chalxanqala village of Babek District, as well as the Oglangala and Alinja Castles, stand out as remarkable defense fortification (1, pag-33).

These monuments spark the interest of tourists visiting Nakhchivan, and they take pleasure in learning about the region's rich history. As people's living standards improve and their worldview and knowledge expand, changes occur in their cultural and social lives. These changes act as key stimuli for the development of cultural tourism. Nowadays, cultural tourism, which generates significant revenue for the economy, enhances the quality of life, and provides more opportunities to learn about the past and present, remains a central focus. It is well known that tourism is one of the most effective means of fostering well-rounded personal development, organizing meaningful and productive leisure time, and encouraging active rest. Tourism is not limited to just enjoying nature's beauty. As a broad and multifaceted social phenomenon, tourism can be studied from three main directions.

The first direction includes travel for educational purposes, meetings with prominent individuals, and exploring historical and architectural monuments, cities, and works of art. The second direction is religious pilgrimages, such as visits to sacred places like Atashgahs, Mecca, Medina, the Kaaba, and other religious sites. The goal here is to broaden individuals' perspectives and enrich their spiritual and human values within the framework of Islamic culture.

The third direction involves travel to places for relaxation and medical treatment. In Azerbaijan, religious pilgrimage sites also have significant tourism value. Holy sites such as shrines, locations associated with important figures in Islamic history, the homes of Seyids, and their graves are popular places for mass visitation. For the integrated use of religious pilgrimage sites, it is advisable to include them in various tourist routes and take visitors to these sacred places according to their preferences.

Among the ancient monuments of Nakhchivan, the sacred site of Ashabi-Kahf holds a special place and significance. This site, mentioned in the Quran, reflected in the works of classical writers, and regarded as a holy pilgrimage destination, is one of the most prominent landmarks of Azerbaijani tourism.

The Ashabi-Kahf mountain and its cave are located 15 kilometers from the city of Nakhchivan, at an altitude of 1605 meters above sea level, between Mount Ilan and Mount Nehecir. The northern slopes of this arc-shaped mountain are steep, while the southern slopes gradually open up. The dome-like, spacious cave exudes an aura of grandeur and mystery. Even thousands of years ago, this cave attracted people with its unique features. It offers a favorable microclimate, a special air current, a natural water source, a distinctive green vegetation cover, and trees growing on the rocks, setting it apart from its surroundings.

Ashabi-Kahf is a natural and historical monument of global significance, having been open to world travelers for centuries. It has long been considered a sacred pilgrimage site. Every year, hundreds of pilgrims from Georgia, Eastern countries, particularly Iran and Turkey, visit this holy place. During the Soviet era, visiting Ashabi-Kahf was restricted, and those who attempted to visit faced persecution and punishment. However, people would still come in secret, often at night, to fulfill their vows, sacrifice animals, and recite prayers.

In the early years of Azerbaijan's independence, under the direction of the national leader Heydar Aliyev, a wide and comfortable road was built to the site, along with a mosque and a bridge. The area was beautified, and favorable conditions were created for pilgrims, transforming Ashabi-Kahf into a true pilgrimage site.

As one of the most prominent monuments of Azerbaijani tourism, Ashabi-Kahf continues to attract the deep interest of travelers as a sacred destination.

Throughout history, people around the world have built monuments to honor the memory of those they revered and valued, eternalizing their spirits. Among the most magnificent of these memorials are mausoleums, with some of the most delicate and luxurious examples in Azerbaijan dating back to the 12th-14th centuries.

The Yusuf Kuseyir oglu and Momine Khatun mausoleums, associated with the renowned Nakhchivan architect Ajami Abubakr oglu, are world-famous monuments. The Yusuf Kuseyir oglu mausoleum, known for its harmonious beauty, is covered with a pyramid-shaped brick dome. Despite its small size and the simplicity of its decorations, the careful con-

struction work makes it an excellent example of architecture. Built in 1162, the architect's name is inscribed on the left side of the entrance. Among the tower-shaped mausoleums in the country, the Yusuf Kuseyir oglu mausoleum is the only one with a pyramid-shaped roof that has remained intact for more than 800 years.

The Momine Khatun mausoleum, constructed by Ajami in 1186 in honor of Momine Khatun, is the most magnificent example of tower-shaped mausoleums in Azerbaijan. Its longevity is attributed to its brilliant engineering. In contrast to its elaborate exterior, the interior of the mausoleum is designed in a more simple style. The structure of the Momine Khatun mausoleum is similar to that of the Yusuf Kuseyir oglu mausoleum.

This mausoleum has attracted the attention of many travelers and scholars who visited Azerbaijan and has been mentioned in numerous works. When French traveler Dubois de Montpereux visited Nakhchivan in the early 19th century, he could not conceal his amazement upon seeing the monument. Professor M.V. Alpatov referred to the Momine Khatun mausoleum as a "Breath of Humanity" (2, p.11).

One of the structures influenced by Ajami's monuments is the Gulustan Mausoleum. The Gulustan Mausoleum was built in the 13th century near Julfa, in the area known as Gulustan, within the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The monuments created by Ajami Abubakr oglu in Nakhchivan not only influenced architecture within Azerbaijan but also left a mark on architects beyond the country's borders. This is evidenced by the argument presented by German orientalist Ernst Diez in his work "The History of Turkish Art" (3, p.48).

The decrees of the Supreme Majlis of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, such as "Organization of the Preservation and Documentation of Historical and Cultural Monuments in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic," "Restoration of the Tomb Monument of Prophet Noah in the City of Nakhchivan," and the creation of the Ordubad "Gamigaya Historical-Artistic Reserve" and the Sharur "Arpachay Historical-Cultural Reserve," have made significant contributions to the study and preservation of historical monuments in the region.

In 2010, a total of 1,197 historical and cultural monuments were registered in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Of these, around 550 are of global and national significance, while the rest are of local importance. Based on these registered monuments, the *Encyclopedia of Nakhchivan Monuments* was compiled. This encyclopedia serves as a crucial resource for the study and promotion of the region's ancient monuments on an international scale.

Every year, thousands of people visit these monuments, and documentaries and films about them further spark public interest. Historical and cultural monuments should be widely used in advertisements to attract tourism to the country.

Thus, the development of tourism in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is closely linked to its rich historical and cultural heritage, architectural examples, religious traditions, ethnographic characteristics,

and other social factors. Expanding historical and cultural tourism in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is of great importance, both for promoting and showcasing the region's ancient history and cultural heritage.

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